

Mercury-mercurous Propionate Electrode

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The feasibility of mercury-mercurous propionate electrode has been investigated. The standard potential of the Hg, Hg₂Pr₂, Pr⁻ electrode at 30° is -0.50005 volt.

Mercury-mercurous chloride and mercury-mercurous sulphate electrodes have been used for a long time. Of the general type of electrodes, Hg, Hg₂X₂ (or Hg₂X⁻), X⁻, the acetate electrode was reported by Larson and McDougal¹. Larson and Tomsicek² and Larson³ further studied the nature of the electrode. Recently Covington *et al.*⁴ have re-determined the standard potential of the acetate electrode at 25°. While studying the nature of the metal propionates in solution, the possibility of an electrode, reversible with respect to the propionate ions, was investigated. From the similarity in the physical properties of mercurous propionate and mercurous acetate, it was considered worthwhile looking into the workability of the mercury-mercurous propionate electrode. Some measurements have been reported in the present communication, showing the reversibility of the propionate electrode. The standard potential of the mercury-mercurous propionate electrode has been determined by setting up cells:

EXPERIMENTAL

Redistilled mercury was distilled again under vacuum. Mercurous chloride used was of chemically pure quality and potassium chloride was of B.D.H. AnalaR quality.

Mercurous propionate was prepared by precipitating it from a mercurous nitrate solution by addition of sodium propionate. The precipitate was filtered on a Buchner funnel and washed under suction with *N*/10 propionic acid solution. After drying under suction, mercurous propionate was kept in a vacuum desiccator.

Sodium propionate solution was prepared by adding equivalent amounts of NaOH and propionic acid solutions. Excess of propionic acid (equivalent amount) was added to the sodium propionate solution to keep it acidic. The pH of the solution was determined with a pH-meter and found to be 4.86.

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1. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1937, **47**, 493.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **61**, 85.

3. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 937.

4. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1964, **60**, 412.

For the concentration cell:

the electrode vessels and the bridge arrangements were of the same type as used by Prasad and co-workers⁵.

Calomel electrodes were set up in the same way as recommended by Hills and Ives⁶. The mercury-mercurous propionate electrodes were also set up in the same manner.

A mercury-mercurous propionate half element was combined with a quinhydrone half element, thus avoiding the liquid junction. The quinhydrone elements were set up using E. Merck quinhydrone, following the method suggested by Clayton and Vosburgh⁷.

The electromotive force of the concentration cells was measured with a Leeds-Northrup K-2 potentiometer. The measurements were taken at the room temperature (30°). The experiments were done in duplicates. The mean readings are recorded in Tables I and II. The E.M.F. readings were accurate within 0.05 mv, the mean deviation being ± 0.05 mv.

TABLE I

Cell: $\text{Hg, Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2; \text{KCl (satd.)} :: \text{NaPr, Hg}_2\text{Pr}_2, \text{Hg}$.

Salt conc. (c).	E.M.F. obs. (mean).	$RT/F \ln c$.	$\Delta\sqrt{c}$.	$*E_{\text{obs.}} + \frac{RT}{F} \ln c - \Delta\sqrt{c}$.
0.01 M	0.3855 volt	-0.1200	0.0030	0.2625
0.02	0.3687	-1.1019	0.0043	0.2625
0.04	0.3521	-0.0839	0.0061	0.2621
0.05	0.3471	-0.0781	0.0068	0.2622
0.06	0.3425	-0.0733	0.0074	0.2618
0.08	0.3366	-0.0658	0.0086	0.2622
0.10	0.3309	-0.0600	0.0095	0.2614

*Extrapolated value = 0.2626 volt at 30°.

TABLE II

Cell: Pt: $\text{H}_2\text{Q-Q}$ propionic acid: $\text{Hg}_2\text{Pr}_2, \text{Hg}$. $RT/F \ln K = -0.29265. 0.6699$ volt.

$$E^\circ_{\text{H}_2\text{Q-Q}} = -$$

Acid conc. (c).	Mean E.M.F.	$RT/F \ln c$.	$E_{\text{H}_2\text{Q-Q}} - E_{\text{obs.}} - RT/F \ln K$ $= E^\circ_{\text{Hg}_2\text{Pr}_2, \text{Pr}^-}$
0.01 M	0.21285 volt	-0.12000	-0.50010
0.02	0.19470	-0.10190	-0.50000
0.04	0.17665	-0.08390	-0.50005
0.05	0.17080	-0.07810	-0.50000
0.06	0.16605	-0.07330	-0.49995
0.08	0.15862	-0.06580	-0.50005
0.10	0.15280	-0.06000	-0.50010

Average $E^\circ_{\text{Hg}_2\text{Pr}_2, \text{Pr}^-} = -0.50005$ volt at 30°.

5. This Journal, 1951, 28, 683.

6. Nature, 1950, 165, 530; J. Chem. Soc., 1951, 311.

7. J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1937, 59, 2414.

The E.M.F. of the cell:

is given by the expression:

$$E_{\text{obs.}} = E_{\text{calc.}} - E_{\text{Pr}^-} = E_{\text{calc.}} - E_{\text{Pr}^-}^{\circ} - RT/F \ln (\text{Pr}^-)$$

where () stands for activity, assuming that the liquid junction potential has been eliminated by use of the saturated potassium chloride salt bridge. Since propionic acid is a weak acid, the concentration of propionate ion in solution may be taken to be equal to that of sodium propionate in the solution. Further, introducing the interionic attraction terms, we have,

$$E_{\text{obs}} + RT/F \ln c - A \sqrt{c} = (E_{\text{calc.}} - E_{\text{Pr}^-}^{\circ}) - Bc$$

where A and B are the constants of the Debye-Hückel equation.

The column 5 of Table I shows the values of $E_{\text{obs.}} + RT/F \ln c - A \sqrt{c}$. This is plotted against c , the concentration, and by extrapolation, the value of $(E_{\text{calc.}} - E_{\text{obs.}})$ is found to be +0.2626 v. The value of $E_{\text{calc.}}$ being -0.2378 v at 30°, $E_{\text{Pr}^-}^{\circ}$ is equal to -0.5004 volt. Thus from the study of the concentration cells, set up by joining a calomel half element with a mercury-mercurous propionate half element through saturated potassium chloride solution bridge, we test the reversibility of the mercury-mercurous propionate electrode and get a value for the standard potential of the same. For a more accurate value of the standard potential, cells without any liquid junction has been studied, setting up the cell: Pt, H₂Q-Q propionic acid: NaPr Hg₂Pr₂, Hg.

The E.M.F. of the cell is given by the expression:

$$E_{\text{obs.}} = E_{\text{H}_2\text{Q-Q}}^{\circ} - RT/F \ln (\text{H}^+) - E_{\text{Pr}^-}^{\circ} - RT/F \ln (\text{Pr}^-).$$

This reduces to

$$E_{\text{Pr}^-}^{\circ} = E_{\text{H}_2\text{Q-Q}}^{\circ} - E_{\text{obs.}} - 2.303 RT/F \log K_{\text{HPr}} (\text{HPr})$$

where K_{HPr} is the dissociation constant of propionic acid. Taking -4.8775 for the value⁸ of $\log K_{\text{HPr}}$ at 30°, $E_{\text{Pr}^-}^{\circ}$ has been calculated. These are shown in column 4 of Table II. The average value of $E_{\text{Hg, Hg}_2\text{Pr}_2, \text{Pr}^-}^{\circ}$ is -0.50005 volts at 30°.

A comparison of the measurements from the two sets, one with a salt bridge and the other without the liquid junction, shows that the scatter of the results in case of the one with salt bridge is more than the one with no junction. The agreement between the values of the standard potential obtained by the two methods is, however, good, being within less than 0.5 mv. This justifies the assumption that the use of a salt bridge eliminates the liquid junction potential for all practical purposes.